

INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA AND CELEBRITIES ON TOURISM AND MARKETING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15606033>

Annotatsiya. Internet va taniqli shaxslarning odamlarga ta'siri mavzusi unchalik ommabop bo'lmaganligi sababli, ushbu maqola mashhur shaxslarning ijtimoiy tarmoqlar orqali ta'sirining asosiy jihatlarini ochishga qaratilgan. Muallif tomonidan o'tkazilgan so'rov natijalariga ko'ra, yoshlarga keksa avloddan ko'ra internet ko'proq ta'sir ko'rsatadi va aksariyat odamlar sayohat qilish uchun ijtimoiy tarmoqlardagi qiziqishlariga qarab, kino va musiqa sohasi rivojlangan mamlakatlarni tanlashadi. Bundan tashqari, ba'zilar mashhur shaxslar tomonidan tavsiya etilgan mahsulotlarni narxi va sifatiga e'tibor bermasdan, uning ayrim kamchiliklari bilan sotib olishga intilishi ko'rsatiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ijtimoiy media, yoshlar, taniqli shaxslar, ta'sir, keksalar.

Аннотация. В связи с тем, что тема влияния Интернета и знаменитостей на людей не так популярна, данная статья призвана раскрыть основные аспекты влияния знаменитостей через социальные сети. По данным опроса, проведенного автором, молодежь больше подвержена влиянию Интернета, чем старшее поколение, и большинство людей выбирают страны для путешествий в зависимости от своих интересов в интернете, выбирая при этом те страны, в которых развита сфера кино и музыки. Кроме того, будет продемонстрировано, что люди, готовые покупать товары, рекомендованные известными людьми, не обращая внимания на их цены и качество, а также некоторые минусы этой темы.

Ключевые слова: социальные сети, молодежь, знаменитости, влияние, пожилые люди.

Abstract. Due to the fact that the topic of the impact of the Internet and celebrities on people is not so popular, this article aims to open the main aspects of influence of celebrities through the social media. According to a survey conducted by the author, young people are more influenced by the Internet rather than older generation and majority of people choose country to travel depending on their interests on media while choosing those in which the sphere of cinema and music is developed. Additionally, it will be demonstrated that individuals eager to buy products recommended by famous people without paying attention to prices and quality with some disadvantages of it.

Keywords: social media, young, celebrity, impact, elderly.

Introduction

The most debatable topic of recent times has been the connection between celebrities in social media and their influence on ordinary people. Human beings are becoming fully addicted to the information they are getting from the Internet without realizing that most of famous people want to take advantage of them. Promotion via networking sites has a large effect on marketing and tourism decision making. Recommendations from celebrities and advertising on the Internet have a huge impact on people's choice in tourism and the way of living. This article aims to show

how celebrities impact on decision making process of people of various ages examining the spheres of the country chosen to visit and the products endorsed by famous people regardless of costs and features.

Discussions and Results

The majority of society choose their tourism destination thanks to social media and celebrities. According to a study by Fotis, social media plays an extremely important role in many aspects of tourism, including getting information, and decision-making behaviours (2012). Recently, more and more people use gadgets regardless of their age difference, yet not everyone is influenced by social platforms.

Figure 1

Note: The study was done by the author based on opinions of people in Uzbekistan which was conducted through a social survey.

It can be seen that the group with the highest influenced rate is young generation, starting from 15 to 25 years. Elderly people (56 and more) are less affected by modern technologies, since the older the person is, the less flexible their thinking is. For the same reason, just vice versa, youngsters are more open-minded as they were already born during Information Age (XXI century), and it should be easier for them to take the devices used nowadays. In the view of psychology, female are more receptive and emotional than man, what makes women being more impacted by celebrities on social media. It is also shown in the survey conducted among two genders in Uzbekistan (look at Figure 2 below)

Figure 2

As famous people have a huge impact on society, most people living in Uzbekistan want to travel or even live in countries such as South Korea, the USA, and Turkey.

Figure 3

Countries where people in Uzbekistan most want to visit, with percentage:

Nowadays, Instagram is the most influential social networking site, through which people broadcast their so-called “ideal” life in a certain country and persuading citizens of others into visiting their. There are many interesting countries in the world for travel and entertainment. But the majority still chooses the above-mentioned countries because of social media. South Korea attracts with its dramas, K-POP, just like Turkey with TV series and music, while the USA attracts with superheroes from movies, NETFLIX, rap, the most influential shows: Met Gala, Grammy Awards, Oscars and so on.

Figure 4

Causes for traveling with percentage:

With the fact that the younger generation focused on modern technology, making them fans of many films, TV series and famous people singing their favorite songs. That is why they choose countries where new films are premiered, where their idols live and countries where well known global shows take place to visit. However, this process gives people the opportunity to be informed about other countries, their culture and traditions, while followers are ready to increase their language skills in order to have a chance to talk with famous people.

Celebrities and the Internet often influence people's decision making on buying certain products. Social networks such as Instagram, TikTok, Telegram, which greatly influence the opinions and psyche of people, do not go unnoticed. Dozens of celebs who started their way of popularity a long time ago when there were no social medias, are actively using the most powerful ones along with young generation (Amichai-Hamburger et al., 2021). It can be seen as a new source of income for those offering and those promoting the service or commodity. Moreover, buying items advertised by famous people will create a certain feeling of comfort and trust, since the ones who purchased have a strong connection with celebrity endorsers (Qiu et al., 2021). The interest of customers for the company making a product cannot help but grow, and consumers will fulfill their desires knowing that they have something in common with the favorite person of them (Erdogan et al., 2001). In contrast to what was mentioned before, there are couple of disadvantages which should be known by fans blindly following their idol. The products recommended sometimes are not of a good quality and usually are not tested by the celebrities putting them forward. The owner of the brand can raise the prices and make it less affordable, making followers spend a fortune on merchandise and other commodities. And if in case with older generation it is almost impossible to make them believe in the usefulness and the quality of the service, young human beings, especially adolescents, can be easily influenced by authorities keeping in mind that “such a famous person as, for instance, Andrey Arshavin, would not use a product of bad quality” mentions Koteneva (2023). Overall, celebrities may have both positive and negative impacts while promoting certain products, mostly affecting on the minds of young ones.

Conclusion

Besides, the aim of this paper was to assess the effect of the Internet and celebs on people's thinking, mainly their choices in tourism sphere and marketing, it has become the summary of both advantages and disadvantages of such effect. Therefore, certain conclusions can be made. From the results of the research it is evident that the younger people are, the higher chance for them to be influenced by famous ones. Instagram, TikTok, YouTube, and Telegram are one of the most powerful networks, through which people show their lives increasing the popularity of such countries as South Korea, the USA, Turkey. Not only that celebrities influence the sector of tourism, they are becoming the ones who advertise different products and services. This act can be understood from positive and negative sides. From one perspective, celebrities promoting the good make it worldwide known and bought by the followers feeling the connection with their famous people. On the other hand, products recommended by popularities are not usually of a good quality what makes people become disappointed in the brand and the person promoted. As this topic is not well developed nowadays, it is hoped that the further research will be done. And more people from west will talk about it, without creating fake advertisement and situation.

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